

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR CULTIVATING NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL QUALITIES IN STUDENTS OF SPECIALIZED BOARDING SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *In the complex times, when globalization is accelerating in the world development, where drastic changes are taking place, studying, analyzing and determining the place of national and universal qualities in moral education, educating the young generation is a historical necessity and a demand of the times. Deep and comprehensive study of national and universal qualities in modern conditions, correct determination of their place and role in the education of the young generation, specific connections between them, customs, rituals, rules it is important to determine the relationship between them. In this article, ideas about national and universal values that are inherited from generation to generation are put forward.*

Keywords: *national and universal human qualities, national traditions, family, neighborhood, moral culture.*

The main goal of the wide-ranging reforms being implemented in our country is to educate the youth of the next generation, who are the creators of our future, in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland and national values. The changes taking place in the world, globalization and the wide spread of different ideological and spiritual morals and behaviors in the age of information threaten education and values in the spirit of national and universal human values. Therefore, the issue of education is a high-ranking issue at the level of state policy, and the main goal of the ongoing large-scale educational reforms is to create a young generation with intellectual potential, relying on national values, alien and destructive. It is to ensure that the children will become uncompromising fighters and high morale individuals.

On the basis of large-scale reforms in the course of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of training the personnel of the future generation of our nation today and tomorrow is considered one of the most important tasks. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, touched on the issue of educating the youth of our country: in his address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020: We must create the environment and conditions that will educate the Khorezmi, Beruniy, Ibn Sina, Ulughbek, Navoi and Babur. It is not for nothing that they stated that, first of all, the development of education and training, the establishment of a healthy lifestyle, and the advancement of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea." [1]

Why is it necessary to educate students in the spirit of national and universal human values in educational institutions? The saying of the Uzbek people, which has been told for years, says, "A bird does what it sees in its nest." Therefore, you can say that education begins first in the family. But I think it is necessary to tell a story here. It is known from history that the Chinese people paid all their attention to the construction of the Great Wall of China for several centuries and mobilized millions of people to build it. The goal was to repel the invading Huns. But they

forgot to educate the next generation as patriots, especially the guards who stand in defense of the Motherland. The Huns bribed the guards and entered the Chinese territory without damaging the wall or themselves. The contribution of the story is that as our country develops, education of specialized boarding school students who are separated from their families in the spirit of national and universal values is one of the urgent issues of the education sector.

S.Bishop[2], one of the foreign scientists, in his scientific views, rejects any opportunity to inculcate values in society, especially schools.

cites three reasons why they should be used, in the following order:

1. The increase of various social and criminal problems in the society is related to the inability to acquire the necessary values;

2. Uncertainty in our social values leads to the loss of our values formed on the basis of historical experience;

3. Influence factors due to negative peer pressure, negative influence of mass media and increasing number of divorces play an important role.

It is important to educate people in the spirit of national and universal values to ensure the continuity of social harmony among students by improving the methodology of educating students in the spirit of national and universal human values. In this place, it represents the basic institutional infrastructure necessary to educate schoolchildren from a young age in the spirit of universal values. In educating schoolchildren in the spirit of national and universal human values, the issue of instilling the spirit of national and universal human values in the curriculum of secondary schools and in the textbooks prepared according to this program has an important place [2].

Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to educating students of specialized boarding schools in the spirit of national and universal human values in history classes.

1. National values are manifested in the language, history, and customs of a nation's personality. The words "nation" and "Uzbek" were expressed on the basis of national values. The word "Millat" means the following three meanings from the Arabic language. First is the sect, second is the ummah, and third is the people. The word nation is defined in the Holy Qur'an as "it is a sin for a representative of each nation to develop its national values, leaving its own nation and people to another nation" [3].

The word "Naatsiya" used in foreign literature means tribe, nation. Being proud of one's nation, one's country, being proud of being a citizen of Uzbekistan, and feeling a sense of national pride is an important part of national value.

The content of national values - our motherland's many years of great historical past, Eastern enlightenment, its contribution to world culture and civilization and its position in it; The achievements of our compatriots, our great ancestors in the field of culture, science, religion, literature, art are of global significance, architectural monuments, Uzbek national customs, traditions, traditions, etc. It is the main goal of the research work to explain and accustom students of specialized boarding schools during the course of the lesson to respect these values, honor them, and honor them [3].

2. Universal values are spiritual wealth belonging to all mankind and peoples of the world. "It is in accordance with the goals and aspirations of all nations, peoples and peoples in the universal aspirations. No people and nations in the world have a separate culture, completely

separated from other peoples and nations, from the world civilization as a whole. Universal human values become universal only when they are integrated with national values" [4].

Universal values include problems such as "developing science on Earth, maintaining peace, stopping the race of nuclear weapons, ensuring international security, preventing various diseases, protecting nature, ending poverty and illiteracy[3].

Universal values never lose their positive significance. Universal human qualities are created on the basis of the above values. Human freedom, the right to life, health, education, social protection in old age and humanity, friendship, doing good, honesty, truthfulness, patriotism, hard work are inherent in every nation. appears characteristically.

As noted by scientists, it is also important to understand the tasks of the public and the teaching profession in educating in the spirit of national and universal values. Because, just as the public should understand the essence of the educational service, the teacher should also understand public opinion and public order. Therefore, education in the spirit of national and universal values is as important as discussing moral principles in education. According to proponents of this view, there cannot be two sets of moral principles, one for life in school and one for life outside of school. Just as behavior is unique, so are principles of behavior. The tendency to discuss school ethics as if the school itself is an institution is very unfortunate. Because the moral responsibility of the school and its leaders rests with society. In essence, the school is an institution created by the society to perform a certain task, to continue life and to perform a certain function to increase the welfare of the society [6].

In particular, in educating students in the spirit of national and universal values, pride, future and historical self-awareness based on national values, historicity, rationality, observation, comparative comparison, and personal attitude to social reality and the moral standards of our ancestors, each nation The existence of the nation's spiritual world plays an important role in understanding its unique national culture and national identity. Therefore, in education in the spirit of national and universal values, national culture is the main condition of national self-awareness, as well as values, such as economic and territorial unity, in defining its essence in the process of formation of a nation.

Education of students in the spirit of national and universal human values is manifested as a legal result of historicism-development, as a moral and moral criterion of the development of society, and it is manifested in the relations of people to nature and social life in the early stages of development. In education in the spirit of national traditions, it is explained as rationality in the self-awareness of the individual, - based on any values, the form and level of the national worldview is expressed through logical combinations. For example, if the logical consistency is broken, the objective, scientific, clear and consistent reflection of the worldview will be undermined. Therefore, in the process of pedagogical scientific research in the educational system, if education serves to bring a person to a higher level, to glorify him, to achieve intellectual and mental maturity, then moral education, his behavior, independent character, personal characteristics development, causes awareness of national identity. Education, morals, universal values are considered to be the factors that serve to realize the national identity in students.

Therefore, in educating students in the spirit of national and universal values, parents and teachers' attempts to morally educate their children and students are also playing an important role. J.E. Udokang[7], a foreign scientist, pays special attention to the issues of educating students based on values through moral education.

Therefore, he wants educational institutions to produce young people with high knowledge and intellect, broad outlook, smart, moral, conscientious, correct words, who respect national and universal values and traditions, and who are patriotic and patriotic. and acts for these purposes. However, this is not an easy task. For this, the issue of instilling in the minds of students through a well-designed educational policy, highly qualified pedagogic teachers, and spiritual and enlightened parents is of great importance.

It is known that today, in the minds of many young people, students and young people who are consumers of society, indifference to the fate of the Motherland and the country, against the negative evils of "mass culture", by educating them in the spirit of national and universal values, as a mature generation for the future destiny coming of age is important. Thanks to the Internet and high technologies in the rapidly developing society, the boundaries between cultures and countries are disappearing. Now, in order to resist information attacks and dangers through more than 60,000 websites that promote corruption through Internet networks, we must first of all inculcate in our students the national values and our high spirituality that have been settled for centuries. It is important to educate the young generation as patriots and leaders in the spirit of national values based on the history, spiritual and cultural heritage of their people.[5]

Most of the students studying in specialized boarding schools are separated from family and social life. What are the pedagogical possibilities of educating them in the spirit of national and universal values? First of all, since virtue is interpreted as the owner of good behavior, what should be paid attention to in order to cultivate such qualities. These are one of our pressing issues today. National values are undoubtedly directly related to the development or crisis of the nation. National values - the only element that ensures the integrity of the nation and distinguishes it from other nations is the "cultural dimension". All the values that we bring from generation to generation from the past to the present are the foundation of our national culture.

It is important to educate our national cultural heritages, architecture and works of art, songs, folk songs, fairy tales, food and drinks, national costumes, folk games, literary works and beliefs with the heritages of our national culture [8] is enough. National values develop along with the development of the nation and depreciate when faced with a crisis. Therefore, the nation must protect, develop and enrich its values in every way. In the sense that national values are constantly being improved in the process of development, the real owner of their values is the main object that conveys them from the past to the future in the process of changes consisting of the development of space and time. Depending on historical necessity, sometimes this value comes to the forefront of social development. For example: when the motherland is invaded - freedom, during war - peace, during colonialism - independence, nationalism, when sick or sick - the value of health increases. National values Education on the basis of universal, national and personal values is important. Values related to the life, lifestyle, language, culture, spirituality, customs and traditions, past and future of a certain people, nation, people are national values [3]. Values that express the most important aspects of nature and society, laws, and relationships in society, based on universal values, education in the spirit of values are eternal values. Values related to a person, his activity, lifestyle, faith, meaning of life, manners, beauty, behavior are personal values.

It serves as the main tool in educating students in the society in the spirit of national and universal values [8]. As mentioned above, the main goal of the scientific work is to improve the methodology of educating students in the spirit of national and universal values based on values.

means and it reflects the pedagogical possibilities of instilling certain values in the minds of students during the lesson or through organizational activities outside the classroom.

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